

CHARACTERISTICS OF NAJMIDDIN KOMILOV'S SCIENTIFIC METHOD.

Elmurad Nasrullaev

Associate Professor of Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Doctor of Philosophy in Philology (PhD)

Phone: +998945710422

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7686916>

Annotation

Navoi's work is based on wisdom and philosophy applied to art. High potential and talent are required to interpret this feature in Navoi's work, which is not found in any representative of our classical literature. That is, it requires a unique style and a unique expression. This article talks about the principles of scientific method and literary-aesthetic research of Najmiddin Komilov, the leading figure in Uzbek Navoi studies.

Key words: Navoi scholar, Sufism, wisdom, lesson, epic, figurative love, eternity, revolution, journey, perfection, Zullisonayn, Persian.

Najmiddin Komilov initially conducted research on theoretical issues of translation and comparative literature, translation history. He studied issues related to the development of textual studies and literary genres. In the following years, the scientist's scientific activity was focused on the history of Sufism, the main directions of Sufism, sects, sharia, and the concepts of truth. In this direction, he revealed the essence of the teachings of Ahmed Yassavi, Najmuddin Kubra, Ibn Arabi, Nasafi, Bahauddin Naqshband.

N. Komilov also left a name as a translator. He translated from Persian to Uzbek the works of scholar Farididdin Attar's "Ilohiynama", Sultan Valad's "Maarif", Aziziddin Nasafi's "Zubdat ul-haqaiq" and Husayn Vaiz Koshifi's "Futuvvatnamai Sultani".

Before talking about the scientist's scientific method, let's talk about the concept of style. The issue of style applies to all areas of science, and today it is studied from different perspectives in world science. Concepts such as scientific way of knowing, scientific way of thinking are often mentioned in studies of philosophy, art, sociology, natural sciences, and philology. The general use of the concept of style in such fields is explained by one of its important features, which is the ability to think scientifically.

Today, scientists interpret the style as a "holographic" concept. The metaphor of the hologram, widely used in modern science, can be explained as follows: in the hologram, which is three-dimensional, the rays returned from each point of the

object give a certain understanding of the whole object. Even if the laser beam is focused on a part, we will see a complete image of the object, even if it is blurred, not only about that part. The larger the piece, the clearer the image, and the smaller it becomes blurry. When this feature of the hologram is used in the theory of style, it is assumed that even a small piece of text contains a number of information such as the style of the author, the style of the period, and the national style. The style begins to appear in minimal text fields. It can be seen from this that in determining the style of a critic or literary critic, it is not necessary to cover all his works, but one can draw certain conclusions about his style through the analysis of a single article or essay devoted to the commentary of a ghazal.

Basically, two different criteria are considered in the style analysis. The first is linguistic, and the second is in accordance with general aesthetics. In the first case, style is more or less understood as a writing style, a system of methods. In fact, today's meaning of the word "style" arose historically on the basis of metonymy. In ancient Greece (Greek *stylos*, Latin *stylus*), later in Rome, a stick-pen was called a style. The end of the stick had a rubber part for erasing mistakes. This is where the phrase "turning the style" came from, which is used to work on mistakes and delete poorly written ones. For this reason, today expressions such as "a critic with his own pen" and "a sharp pen" can be used in the sense of "having his own style". In this way, the concept of style was formed as a characteristic feature of writing, a system of methods. This is a descriptive approach, and although it has several advantages in style analysis, it is not sufficient to rely on it alone when defining style.

Most theoreticians consider style as "meaningfulness of form". So, when we talk about style, we mean not only the originality of form, but also the content of the content hidden behind that originality.

Another English scholar, Nelson Goodman, in his research on style, considers style as a signature and considers external factors to be primary in determining the artist's style. In this, he focuses mainly on the use of words and phrases, because the critical work of a scientist is aimed at the public, so the use of words and phrases is also important in determining the critic's style.

In Uzbek literary studies, a number of studies have been created that shed light on the creative style, how it manifests, and its unique characteristics (A. Fitrat, A. Sa'diy, I. Sulton, A. Hayitmetov, B. Valikho'jaev, R. Vahidov, D. Salohi, Q Ergashev).

The method of orientation, which reflects the general scientific-aesthetic relations of most scientists, covers the method of analysis and sets before us the task of analyzing whether the critic used analytical methods appropriately and skillfully.

As for the style of the narcissist scientist N. Komilov, regardless of whether the scientist analyzes a part of the artistic text or approaches each work as a whole, he always puts forward his scientific and theoretical views based on the laws of aesthetics, using various methods. We think that the following recognition of professor Rahim Vahidov (r.) can be a proof of our opinion: "Najmiddin's review of ghazals, studies on Sufism are rare events in our scientific life armed with the ideology of independence." In addition, "in Najmiddin's scientific observations, translation and mysticism always stand side by side, like the two fruitful bodies of a single tree."

For example, many ironic symbols, symbolic words and the secret of hidden meanings behind them, such as love, may, maykhana, kharobot, soqi, sogar, kadah, khum, mahbub, which are found in the works of the Navoi scientist poet, are examined in the unity of his creative environment. And focuses on the fact that the content can be clarified as necessary only if it is interpreted in the context of human observations.

The Navoiist scholar proves this point by analyzing the great poet's ghazal titled "Grief to the end of the bow and cunning" and tries to reveal the mystical meanings of this ghazal.

Although this ghazal is not from the outside and is dedicated to the description of its characteristics, according to the scientist, in the ghazal, the poet mentioned the divine love - enlightenment, the culmination of the desire for knowledge, the strong pleasure that appeared in the lover's tongue at the sight of Yor Jamoli - a symbolic expression of inspiration, joy, and surur. And being slanderous, slanderous is also appropriate here. According to the scientist, visiting the great source of light is the intoxicating feeling of enjoying life, the beauty of nature, and the miracle of the Absolute Spirit, which does not think or think, but is felt with the heart.

The scientist relates this to the fact that, according to the philosophical doctrine of Naqshbandi, which Navoi believed in, the universe is a mirror created by the eternal and eternal Spirit's desire to love itself and look at its own beauty. For example, the light radiated from the radiance of the primary power is reflected in this mirror, that is, the entire existence and creation of the material world -

from the particle to the sun, the earth is blue, the fixed planet is illuminated by this light, it moves due to this light, and a certain harmony develops within. According to the Navoi scholar, the poets took this divine symbol in the form of May.

Here, the scientist reveals that in Sufi poetry it is called the material world or the cup, and notes that the colors of the world, all the splendor of life, the storm of beauty that appears to be raging are explained as the waves and foaming of this ocean of may, and the human being is also a part of this mirror, but the Spirit is Absolute. Draws attention to the fact that it is considered as the most reflected type. To prove this, Mawlana quotes Bedil's definition of a person, that is, a person is considered to be "the sum of the talents of two worlds".

The development of the scientist in revealing the essence of the human soul is that it constantly strives towards its source, and because this striving takes place through the perception of the world itself and self-awareness, a person is endlessly amazed by observing the beauty of the phenomena of the world.

Continuing his thoughts on this topic, the scientist notes that since human nature is made up of two elements - the spiritual and the material world, there is a constant struggle between these elements. He notes that in order to prevent this danger, a person should satisfy his spiritual and spiritual needs in the process of development, and it is necessary to train this aspect. As a pir or arif, the people of Sufism meant a wise man with mature intellect, enlightened heart with the light of enlightenment, pure intentions, and pure morals. At the same time, the scholar emphasizes that the pir should be a kind, sympathetic, all-round person for the murid.

According to the scientist, in the eyes of Navoi, Jami was such a person. Such persons always thought of goodness and raised the people who followed them with generosity, strengthened their will, opened the eyes of the soul, taught them to understand the world in a new way, to protect the right path.

The scholar who noted that these meanings are expressed in Hazrat Navoi's poem "Grieving and desha ayori" of Hazrat Navoi tries to explain it with clear explanations:

You can't reach the tip of the bow and you're cunning,
It is the architect of the tavern tomin sun.

The scientist emphasizes the need for explanation of words and phrases such as gamu andesha ayyar, sun architect, kamand, maykhana in the ghazal's matla, and draws attention to the mystical meanings they are used in Sufism literature: although kamand poetry is often used as a metaphor instead of yar hair, in this

place Navoi sees its original dictionary meaning as a rope. Held G'amu andesha means cleverness, cleverness. The scientist refers to various sources to reveal the meaning of the Maykhana istilah, including, according to Sayyid Ja'far Sajjadi's description, "a perfect person full of joy and divine enlightenment is the absolute source of the inner world and soul of a scholar." Sun architect, i.E. The master of creation, means Allah in Sufism. After explaining the meaning of the above mystical terms, the scholar interprets the content of the verse as follows: Hazrat Navoi refers to the habit of throwing a rope on the top of high buildings, palaces and fortresses and climbs onto the roof, saying: He built his roof so great and high that the rope of his thoughts and worries does not reach the tip of his kungura.

The scientist draws attention to the fact that the soul of a scholar is seen as a means and a bridge that leads to the highest state, drawing attention to the fact that Navoiyibora-symbols always have two meanings - the heart of a scholar and the soulful soul - and notes that the poet emphasizes in this verse that it is impossible to conquer the fortress of the house with intelligence and action, because , according to Sufi literature, only the heart and soul are capable of perceiving the enlightenment of the sage's heart and through it the incomparable beauty of the source of the divine soul; in mental observation, the logical-thinking way of knowing is not capable of this.

Scientist Alisher puts forward the opinion that Navoi's ghazal has stated one of the main requirements of Sufism. As a proof of this, the demand is the first serious problem for a person who steps on the path of the order, because to achieve what the mind is not capable of with the will - rebuilding the spiritual will, considering oneself responsible to one's own conscience and faith, and putting it under strict control, too many worldly desires. It means giving up desires. The scientist comes to the conclusion that the reason for the greatness of the Maykhana castle is the great number of mysteries, wonders, and events of the universe, the difficulty of knowing it, getting to its essence, and at the same time, it means the difficulties of overcoming the whims of the ego and being a high moral person.

It seems that in a close analysis of this single verse, we see a number of aspects of the scholar's style, including a deep penetration of the text, a deep scientific interpretation of every point presented.

Considering that all great things are made of small things, and the atom is made up of very small particles, the style of the critic should be understood in the same sense. As the rivulets join together to form a river, all these small means of

description combine to form the style of a literary critic. That's why we are approaching the truth if we say that the spiritual world, worldview, idea, aesthetic ideal of the creator-critic is reflected in his thinking, in his attitude to each artistic text.

Navoiist scientist D. Salakhi states that he discovered an artistic compositional art, which is sometimes overlooked in the oriental poetics of the wise scholar, but which is clearly and perfectly manifested in the great Navoi's poetic style and ghazal: "Ghazals with such a structure and content (that is, ghazals without a single plot line - E.N.) by researchers, it was understood as gazelles in confusion. In the eyes of the scientist, this is a rather superficial and one-sided conclusion. His point of view is different: "Frankly speaking, I am against applying the term "disorder" to poetry. Because disorganization is not a characteristic of a work of art, it refers to a collection of stanzas that are not completely connected. Great poets, including Navoi, do not have such a poem. Although the stanzas, on the surface, seem to be unrelated in content, on different topics, inwardly they are related. Therefore, in the analysis of such ghazals, I think it is better to use the concepts of direct connection (musalsal) and indirect connection. The scientist calls the ghazals written in the method under analysis as ghazals written in the "negation-affirmation" method. In fact, only a poet who has searched for a deep meaning in a ghazal and accepted it as an expression of a single idea in different ways and methods can make a correct statement in this regard. In particular, he feels that the art of "denial-affirmation" is very beautiful, folk, light humor, and pleasant, like a young child's complaint.

Wisdom, as we mentioned, is a combination of science and inner feeling in Navoi's poetry. Science gives shape to sense. As the well-known scientist Ibrahim Haqqul explained, "The most difficult and complicated thing is to enter the path of meaning, to be a lover of essence." D. Completing his comments, Salahi writes: "An admirer must not be able to understand the form of the poem - rhyme, radif, weight, allusion, tajni." Meaning enters the mind. The image can be flirtatious, fun, or sad. The mind perceives meaning through form. However, if the form is incomplete and incomplete, if the heart does not enjoy it, that is, if there is intelligence and no feeling, then wisdom will not be fully revealed.

In his own research on the interpretation of "Khamsa" epics, scientist Navoi carries out their optimal, complete analysis, the ability of the scientist to work on the basis of consistent logic, the ability to select very important considerations for today's reader from the core of a great work, and also. The

characteristic of the scientist's style - the ability to see the essence - becomes clear. For example, in the article entitled "Hikmat va ibrat dostoni" from his monograph called "Khizr Chashmami", Hazrat Navoi interprets "Saddi Iskandarii", the last and largest epic of "Khamsa" from the perspective of Sufism, and refers unexpected developments to the judgment of the readers. .

It is known that many studies have been conducted by Navoi scholars on the works of Alisher Navoi, including his epic "Saddi Iskandari". However, N. Komilov, a major representative of this field, notes that the philosophical-philosophical aspect of this work is neglected in the existing studies, and draws attention to the fact that the depth of Navoi's artistic thinking is highlighted at this point.

The scientist shows that the main idea of the great poet expressed in this epic is that Alexander the Conqueror, who took the world, died like a weak servant and entered the grave like a beggar with nothing. He points out that it is shown as an example to the kings and princes who quarrel and cause concern to the people. From this point of view, it is noted that Alexander is a symbol of great educational importance both in those times and now.

In the epic "Saddi Iskandari", the scholar noted that after Alexander's conversation with Gado, Alexander's question to Aristotle is about who, which status is closer to the goal and which path is more appropriate to reach this status, and how Aristotle said that the status of non-existence is the right path and showed the way to achieve it easily. Enough, he emphasizes that it is about the status of Sufism. In Hikmat, to Alexander's question about what is the highest goal of a person, and the result of which work is praiseworthy and good, Navoi quotes the following verse from the language of Aristotle:

Деди: халқдин ўзни фард айламак,
Фано кўйи йўлинда гард айламак

That is, the main goal is to separate oneself from the people and become the soil of the path of destruction. This is the path of dervishes and saints. In his answer, Aristotle said that there is a second way to achieve this high goal - an acceptable way for property owners, and he says that it is to do good and meritorious deeds in the society and become a devotee of the Righteous. The scientist notes that Navoi's belief that "Whoever generates more merits, he can hope for more blessings" is reflected in this, and he also emphasizes that it is recommended to do good deeds in one's own position, in one's place. After all, the work that is not in its place will not be successful. The scholar notes that here Navoi is referring to Sufism requirements such as futuvat, generosity, forgiveness, and

compassion. At the same time, the scientist Navoi said that a rich person should not indulge in showing generosity to the farmer, but should do all the work wholeheartedly and earnestly, freeing himself from anger, lust, arrogance, and selfishness. He states that if he accepts his faith and still has human behavior, he can reach the Godhead, and then the goal will be formed. It should be noted that the scientist is interested in such a question, so he expresses his intention to make Sufism the program of his life, and the important thing is that this program will be carried out by the world-loving king.

References:

1. Davlatova, M. H. (2019). Variability of Aspectual Meanings in English. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Science*, 7(12.2019), 778-780.
2. Davlatova, M. H. (2020). An Integrative history of Aspectual meanings. *JournalNX*, 6(04), 17-22.
3. Davlatova, M. H. (2020). Aspectual variability of information culture in the history of the English language. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(3), 24-28.
4. Davlatova, M. H. (2020). Lexico-semantic Structure and Its Analysis on the Example of Verbs. *JournalNX*, 6(06), 189-192.
5. Davlatova, M. H. Relation of lexical-semantic structure of verbs in the linguistic essence. *IEJRD-International Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(5).
6. Hasanovna, D. M. (2021). SEMANTIC IMPLEMENTATION OF RESULTATIVE STRUCTURES. *METHODS*, 7(6).
7. Давлатова, М. Х. (2015). The role of songs in learning English. *Молодой ученый*, (10), 1145-1147.
8. Hasanovna, D. M. (2021). DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF RESULTATIVE STRUCTURES ACCORDING TO THEIR LINGUISTIC ESSENCE. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 2 (05), 475-479.
9. Давлатова, М. Х. (2017). Этапы работы с видеотекстами на занятиях Английского языка. *Интернаука*, (9-2), 16-19.
10. Давлатова, М. Х. (2015). The role of songs in learning English. *Молодой ученый*, (10), 1145-1147.
11. Hasanovna, D. M. (2019). VARIABILITY OF ASPECTUAL MEANINGS IN ENGLISH. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 7.
12. Hasanovna, D. M. (2021). Linguistic and cognitive features of performing effective actions. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 3(10), 41-44.

13. Давлатова, М. Х. (2018). РАБОТА НАД ВИДЕОТЕКСТОМ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА. Теория и практика современной науки, (4), 242-246.
14. Давлатова, М. (2020). ASPECTUAL AND LEXICO-SEMANTIC CLASSIFICATION OF VERBS. Сўз санъати халқаро журнали, 1.
15. Hasanovna, D. M. (2021). DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF RESULTATIVE STRUCTURES ACCORDING TO THEIR LINGUISTIC ESSENCE. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 2(05), 475-479.
16. Hasanovna, D. M. (2022). Aspectual and lexical-semantic classification of verbs. *JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*, 8(2), 116-121.
17. Shadmanov, K. B., Davlatova, M. H., Ostonova, S. N., & Radjabova, A. T. (2020). ENGLISH RENAISSANCE: TRANSFORMATION OF 61 PHILOSOPHY UNDERSTANDING AS A FACTOR OF INFORMATION CULTURE DEVELOPMENT OF THE EPOCH. *Cross-Cultural Studies: Education and Science*, 5(1), 61-67.
18. Давлатова, М. Х. Работа над видеотекстам на занятиях Английского языка. Теория и практика современной науки, 242-246.
19. Hasanovna, D. M. (2022). ASPECTUAL AND LEXICAL-SEMANTIC CLASSIFICATION OF VERB NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS *JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal* ISSN No: 2581-4230.
20. Hasanovna, D. M. (2022). Resultative and Causative Meanings in English and Uzbek Languages. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 297-302.
21. Hasanovna, D. M. (2022). ON THE INTERRELATIONSHIP OF RESULTIVE AND CAUSATIVE MEANINGS. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 9, 212-215.
22. Давлатова, М. Х. (2021). THE EXPRESSION OF RESULTATIVE AND DEPICTIVE CONSTRUCTIONS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(5).
23. Davlatova, M. X. (2018). THE EASY WAY OF LEARNING ENGLISH WITH THE HELP OF SONGS. Теория и практика современной науки, (4), 578-581.
24. Hasanovna, D. M. (2021). Semantic Implementation of resultative structures. *novateur publications JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*.
25. Давлатова, М. Х. (2013). Хорошее поведение-важный способ формирования личности. *Вестник Таджикского национального университета*, (3-6), 237-241.

ITALY

ITALY

26. Hasanovna, M. D. (2022). TYPOLOGY OF EXPRESSIVE EMOTIONAL AND LINGUISTIC FEATURES. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 2(11), 65-69.
27. Davlatova, M. K. (2021). THE PROCESS OF TRANSFORMATION OF PHILOSOPHY UNDERSTANDING AS FACTOR OF INFORMATION CULTURE OF THE PERIOD OF THE ENGLISH RENAISSANCE (XVI C.). Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(5), 949-957.
28. Давлатова, М. Ҳ. (2021). РЕЗУЛЬТАТИВЛИКНИНГ АСПЕКТУАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ДОИРАСИДА ЎРГАНИЛИШИ. Scientific progress, 2(2), 1678-1683.
29. Давлатова, М. (2020). FE'LLARNING ASPEKTIK VA LEKSIK-SEMANTI K TASNIFI. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 3(1).
30. Muhayyo, D. (2017). THE ROTOR CONSTRUCTION OF COTTON RAW IN APPEARING VERTICAL BOUNDARY. Интернаука, (9-2), 76-78.
31. Davlatova, M. H. RELATION OF LEXICAL-SEMANTIC STRUCTURE OF VERBS TO RESULTABILITY.
32. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). THE MAIN CONCEPTS OF POLITENESS IN MODERN LINGUOPRAGMATICS: THE POLITENESS PRINCIPLE BY J. LEECH. International Journal of Pedagogics, 2(11), 15-20.
33. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF DISCOURSE ELEMENTS AS INDICATORS OF POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE EVALUATIONS. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 2(12), 55-63.
34. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER-DETERMINED DIFFERENCES IN THE SPEECH OF LITERARY CHARACTERS. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(12), 210-215.
35. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER ELEMENT OF SPEECH BEHAVIOR FROM THE POSITION OF TEXT ORGANIZATION MECHANISMS. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(13), 274-281.
36. Джалилова, З. (2022). ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ВЗГЛЯД НА МЕЖЛИЧНОСТНОЕ ОБЩЕНИЕ. Zamonaviy dunyoda ilm-fan va texnologiya, 1(7), 331-336.
37. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER XUSHMUOMALALIKKA ASOSLANGAN IBORALARNING SHAKLLANISHI. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 1(28), 303-308.
38. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & SHARIPOV, A. G. ALPHABET OF LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 338-339.

39. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & UBAJDULLOEV, A. U. U. COMPARISON DEGREES OF ADJECTIVES IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО "Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 336-338.
40. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & JAKUBOV, U. S. NUMBERS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО "Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 339-341.
41. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & ALIEV, M. N. ADJECTIVE IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО "Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 332-334.
42. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & ALIEV, M. N. PRONOUNS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО "Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 334-336.
43. DJALILOVA, Z. O., & KHAYOTOV, K. M. K. U. LATIN PRONOUNS. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО "Издательство Молодой ученый", (53), 257-258.
44. DJALILOVA, Z. O., & KHAYOTOV, K. M. K. U. LATIN PRONOUNS. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО "Издательство Молодой ученый", (53), 257-258.
45. Djalilova, Z. O. (2023). A DISCOURSIIVE TURN IN THE THEORY OF LINGUISTIC POLITENESS: TO THE FORMATION OF THE THEORY OF LINGUISTIC IMPOLITENESS. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(02), 15-23.
46. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2022). STRONG PERSONALITY'S ARTISTIC AND POETIC REFLECTION IN THE RENAISSANCE EPOCH. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 2(11), 43-51.
47. nafisa Zayniddinovna, T. (2022). Lexico-Semantic Word Production as a Way of Forming Theater Terminology of the English Language. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(10), 144-150.
48. Zayniddinovna, T. N., & Sharofiddinovich, S. S. (2021). General cultural and educational values of ancient-classic latin language. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 2(5), 77-80.
49. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2023). CHARACTERIZATION OF THE IMAGE OF AMIR TEMUR IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S DRAMA "TAMERLANE THE GREAT". International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(02), 36-43.
50. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF MALE AND FEMALE ORAL SPEECH IN MODERN ENGLISH. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 2(10), 14-21.

